

INFLUENCE OF CORONAVIRUS INFECTION COVID-19 TO A ECHOCARDOGRAPHIC CHANGES IN PATIENTS WITH A SURVEY OF PNEUMONIA

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Relevance: COVID-19 has a wide range of cardiac manifestations during the acute phase of the disease. In particular, an elevated level of troponin ranges from 8 to 28%, however, signs of obvious systolic myocardial dysfunction are rarely detected, subclinical myocardial dysfunction is much more often determined in the form of a decrease in global longitudinal strain of the left ventricle (LV) (LV GLS, left ventricular longitudinal strain) – during the period of hospitalization, it is demonstrated by up to 80% of patients [1]. LV GLS has been shown to be a strong independent predictor of in-hospital mortality [2] and therefore may be critical for risk stratification at follow-up.

Target: to compare clinical and echocardiographic parameters in patients with proven COVID-19 pneumonia, depending on the magnitude of global LV longitudinal strain (LV GLS) one year after discharge.

Material and research methods: The recruitment of patients was carried out from September 2021 to February 2022. All examined gave written informed consent to participate. Inclusion criteria: documented diagnosis of COVID-19-associated pneumonia, willingness of the patient to participate in observation. Exclusion criteria: chronic diseases in the acute stage, a history of oncological diseases lasting less than 5 years, tuberculosis and other diseases accompanied by pneumofibrosis, HIV, hemodynamically significant heart defects, chronic hepatitis. Exclusion criteria: unsatisfactory imaging on echocardiography (EchoCG), dilated, restrictive and hypertrophic cardiomyopathy, pregnancy detected during the observation period, oncological diseases, refusal to participate.

Conclusions. Inhibition of LV GLS one year after COVID-19 pneumonia was detected in 58.6% of patients with normal LV EF. In the group with impaired LV GLS, men predominated, IHD was more often detected in combination with hypertension, and LV diastolic function indicators were worse compared to the group with normal LV GLS.

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